

Introduction

In recent decades, digital applications have revolutionised archaeological practice, serving as invaluable tools for studying sites, records, and promoting heritage through new methods able to fascinate new audiences like AR, VR, and video games (Bekele et al. 2018; Champion 2015; Champion 2021; Sanders 2014). More recently, the academic community, including archaeology professionals, has shown great interest in the relationship between digital games, research, education, and outreach (Ariese et al. 2021; Hageneuer 2020; Huggett 2019; Mol et al. 2017; Morgan 2019; Reinhard 2018) since, as pointed out by Champion (2015), these digital products offer a learning potential through tools focused on non-textual visualisation, in addition to their ability to convey stories and meanings by applying mechanisms able to engage the large public into an active state of lasting commitment and learning where players are motivated to create their own knowledge rather than to receive information passively (Mortara et al. 2014: 318).

The integration of video games with archaeology in Italy has been challenging due to academics viewing commercial products as providing unreliable information, the misconception that video games are childish entertainment, and the lack of understanding of the interactive industry by archaeologists (Giordano 2020; Modena 2019). Meanwhile, commercial interactive media producers have been meeting the public's desire for historical representations, but they often lack the expertise to meet archaeologists' high content standards (Mariotti 2020a).

However, the recent institutionalization of Public Archaeology programs in Italy (Bonacchi 2013) had the potential to face the interactive entertainment industry's encroachment into archaeology (Richardson 2013) and change these sentiments towards interactive entertainment (De Felice 2015; Volpe 2020; Volpe and De Felice 2014). As a result, the domain of cultural and archaeological heritage in Italy has recently seen an upsurge of interest in video games. This is largely due to the attention from museums and academics (Bertoldi and Mariotti 2022; Bonacini 2023; Bonacini and Giaccone 2022; Pescarin 2020) as well as the incentives provided for digital innovation by local administrations and the government (First Playable Found 2021).

The National Research Council of Italy has played a pivotal role in the development of video games that promote archaeological sites over the years (Pescarin 2020: 11-13; Pietroni 2020). As 3D and interactive technologies become more affordable and easy to use, private companies and archaeological departments are increasingly involved in this field - even internationally as in the case of Valeté Vos Viatores video game project (Andreu Pintado et al. 2022). This led to a significant increase in the creation of such games and their accessibility to the public. Moreover, it is now possible to cater to the growing demand by including a larger number of lesser-known archaeological sites, museums, and themes.

Various samples of recent archaeogaming projects in Italy, with clear promotional and educational purposes, are presented in Table 1, including examples retrieved from scientific literature and the Italian Videogame Program narrative archive (IVIPRO 2023).

Typology	Title Example	Content	Research	Tech. Development	References
trivia, puzzles and mini-games	<i>Time Tales – The Etruscans</i> (2019)	educational game for children dedicated to the Etruscan civilization	Archeokids	Entertainment Game Apps Ltd.	Mariotti and Marotta 2020
gamified solutions of interactive exhibitions/visits	<i>Aquileia 3D</i> (2014)	mobile AR application created to enhance the Roman past of Aquileia	Fondazione Aquileia, University of Padova	Ikon Company, Nudesign	https://www.fondazioneaquileia.it/it/visita-aquileia/aquileia-3d https://www.ikon.it/it/progetti/antica-aquileia-3d
gamified solutions of interactive exhibitions/visits	<i>ArkaeVision Archeo</i> (2018)	a mixed gamified experience (VR and MR) dedicated to the ancient city of Paestum	National Research Council of Italy	Digitalcomœdia, Beyond Tech.	Pagano et al. 2020
gamified solutions of interactive exhibitions/visits	<i>Inventum</i> (2018)	mobile AR application created to promote the National Archaeological Park of Venosa, Potenza	Effenove s.r.l.s.	Effenove s.r.l.s., Pixel s.r.l., Jetbit Digital Agency	https://www.inventumgame.com/

mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Father & Son</i> (2017)	a narrative 2D game created for the National Archaeological Museum of Naples	National Archaeological Museum of Naples, Tuo Museo	Tuo Museo	Solima 2018
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Mi Rasna</i> (2018)	a simulation game dedicated to the Etruscan civilization	Etruscan Museum of Villa Giulia (+ national and local museums, various Superintendencies), Entertainment Game Apps Ltd.	Entertainment Game Apps Ltd.	Amoroso 2020 Bonacini and Giaccone 2022
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Past for Future</i> (2018)	a narrative 2D game created for the promotion of the ancient city of Taranto	National Archaeological Museum of Taranto, Tuo Museo	Tuo Museo	https://museotaranto.beniculturali.it/en/past-for-future/
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Beyond Our Lives</i> (2019)	an adventure game to promote the main ancient Etruscan cities in Tuscany	Tuo Museo	Tuo Museo	https://www.beyondourlives.com/
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Dive in the Past</i> (2021)	an adventure game developed as part of an European project to promote the underwater archaeological heritage	Campi Flegrei Archaeological Park, Central Institute for Restoration, University of Zara, Greek Ephorate, Ministry of Greek Culture	3D Research s.r.l.	Cozza <i>et al.</i> 2021
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Domitian</i> (2021)	a narrative puzzle game dedicated to the exhibition "Emperor Domitian: God on Earth"	University of Newcastle, Rijksmuseum van Oudheden	Entertainment Game Apps Ltd.	https://www.egameapps.com/gameapps/domitian/
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Hold the Hut</i> (2021)	a puzzle game dedicated to the discovery of a VI century B.C. hut on the site of Serra a San Chirico Nuovo, Potenza	Soprintendenza Archeologia Belle Arti e Paesaggio della Basilicata	Effenove s.r.l.s.	Mutino <i>et al.</i> 2022
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Mediterranean</i> (2021)	a simulation game developed as part of an European project dedicated to the Phoenician civilization	La Rotta dei Fenici, Entertainment Game Apps Ltd.	Entertainment Game Apps Ltd.	https://www.egameapps.com/gameapps/mediterranean/
mobile applications for museums, touristic sites, exhibitions exploiting some reward/engagement mechanism	<i>Taras' Gifts</i> (2022)	a narrative game created during the Covid pandemic for the exhibition "Taras and the Gifts of the Sea" at the Archaeological Museum of Taranto	University of Bari	Swipe Story	De Felice 2022
virtual simulations of past events through gesture based interaction	<i>Difendiamo le Mura!</i> (2014)	a virtual simulation game based on the siege of the city of Paestum by Alexander Molossus and available inside the local archaeological museum	National Research Council of Italy, Fondazione Paestum, University of Salerno	E.V.O.CA. s.r.l., National Research Council of Italy	Pietroni 2020

adventures set in faithful reconstructions and/or digital counterparts of real sites	<i>A Night in the Forum</i> (2019)	an environmental narrative game for Sony PlayStation VR set in the Forum of Augustus, Rome	National Research Council of Italy, Museo dei Fori Imperiali	VRTRON, National Research Council of Italy	Ferdani <i>et al.</i> 2020 Pescarin <i>et al.</i> 2020
mixed experience (gaming, VR and AR) to explore and play in reconstructed archaeological sites	<i>Augustus</i> (2022)	app-game and PC game dedicated to four archaeological parks in Sicily	University of Palermo, National Research Council of Italy	ETT, Red Raion, AD Meridiam	Fazio <i>et al.</i> 2022 https://www.augustusgame.it/

Table 1: Some relevant archaeogaming examples in Italy in the last decade.

This paper presents a video game project, *The Living Hill*, developed within the Department of Historical Sciences and Cultural Heritage of the University of Siena. The game is dedicated to the excavation site located on the Poggio Imperiale hill of Poggibonsi (Siena, Italy) (Francovich and Valenti 2007) which has been an emblematic case study for digital application to an archaeological project since its initial phases in the 1990s (Fronza *et al.* 2000) and the case study chosen to experiment with new dissemination methodologies such as VR and gaming applied to archaeological heritage in the last three years (Bertoldi 2021; Bertoldi and Mariotti 2022; Mariotti 2020b). *The Living Hill* was developed starting from the scientific results of the Poggibonsi excavation and through a strict collaboration between academia and industry (Entertainment Game Apps, Ltd., the company that managed the programming and the graphic of the game is specialised in historical video games) in the framework of the C.A.P.I. project (Collina Accessibile di Poggio Imperiale - Accessibility of the Hill of Poggio Imperiale) whose aim was the digital enhancement of the archaeological heritage on the site. What is extraordinary in this case study is the nature of the archaeological context (spanning from Late Antiquity to the First Renaissance period) and the evident intentions in terms of public outreach that characterized the excavation project since the earliest approaches: from the creation of the archaeological park in 2007 to the building of the open-air museum (in 2014) which pursues an in-progress full-scale reconstruction of the 17 structures found during the excavation of the Carolingian Age village (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The open-air museum on the hill of Poggibonsi. The remains of the XII century Church of Saint Agnes columns are still visible behind the huts.

After almost 30 years of archaeological research and interpretation on the site, the C.A.P.I. project faced a major challenge: how to use complex archaeological data, often related to small or poorly preserved structures, in a video game that would engage a broad range of learners in accessible ways? In a 2017 paper discussing whether archaeologists and games could mix, Erik Champion concluded: “My solution is to suggest that rather than concentrate on the technology, archaeologists should focus on the expected audience. What do we want to show with digital technology, for what purpose, for which audience, and how will we know when we have succeeded?” (Champion 2017).

In this statement, the author highlights three key issues regarding the use of video games in archaeology that will be used as research questions and guidelines in this paper to illustrate *The Living Hill* project and its preliminary outcomes. First, different professionals with specific competencies are essential for a good result. Archaeologists should focus on historical and archaeological content, narrative, and storytelling, while other professionals should determine the technological aspects (Copplestone 2017). Nevertheless, this also means that since we, as archaeologists, are entering an entirely new way of communicating, we must at least understand the “new rules” of the video game form. Secondly, over the last decade, public engagement and communication of archaeological data have become significant concerns in Italian archaeology (Ripanti 2022). As a result, multiple strategies have been developed, utilizing various mediums, with technology playing a central role (Economou 2015; Moscati 2019). However, as archaeologists, we should focus on exploring the benefits of a gaming approach in expanding communication and outreach through education programs. To do this, a preliminary assessment of the public, themes, and objectives is essential. Lastly, it appears increasingly crucial to set out an experimental approach to evaluate the projects once finished and assess users’ experience and the dissemination/education outcomes of the created video game (Bonacchi and Moshenska 2015: 9).

Connecting Audiences, Objectives and Methods

Following Champion’s questions, one of the first issues we had to face when the C.A.P.I. project started in April 2020 concerned the identification and involvement of the public and the co-creation approach we had planned for the project development. We had scheduled an in-depth analysis of potential users (local community, middle and high school students, archaeology students, academics, and tourists) to collect suggestions and recommendations and to evaluate style choices that had to be made (Bollwerk 2015; Simon 2010: 187). Unfortunately, the Covid-19 pandemic and the subsequent lockdown forced us to change our plans. However, luckily, the open-air museum, in six years of activity, had provided us with a lot of valuable data concerning its heterogeneous public. Official data on tourist trends in Poggibonsi show continuous growth over the years since the creation of the open-air museum: from 42,453 visitors in 2014 to 73,849 in 2018. After a little downturn in 2019 (64,785 visitors) and the expected drastic drop in 2020 (19,522), visible growth is already attested (32,236 visitors in 2021 and 51,462 in 2022) (Camera di Commercio Arezzo-Siena 2023). The archaeological park, which includes the whole surface of the hill, is always open to the public, and every Sunday, archaeologists/reenactors who manage the area are there in their early-medieval costumes, ready to interact with visitors. Moreover, special events are organised throughout the year and, most of all, the open-air museum has become one of the most popular destinations for school trips. Thousands of students come every spring from all over Tuscany and beyond (1,150 students in 2016, 1,800 in 2017, 4,500 in 2018, 4,000 in 2019 according to museum records). In 2023, after three years of stopping, an incredible number of schools booked their visit, and from February to June, about 6,000 students arrived in Poggibonsi. Another aspect that can be noted in the last two years is that, despite its dramatic effects, the Covid-19 pandemic had a positive impact on many schools’ digital assets by forcing them to upgrade their technological equipment (Giovannella *et al.* 2022). Although interactive whiteboards (IWBs) were already quite common (Piano Nazionale Scuola Digitale 2015), various schools received funding to purchase tablets and computers to facilitate remote learning. However, the digital gap is still a persistent issue in Italy, particularly in peripheral areas (Di Pietro 2021).

Based on these data and through interviews and focus groups with the archaeologists who manage the open-air museum, interact with visitors and collect their impressions (Valenti and Salzotti 2017), a list of appreciated features was created. These were combined with project objectives established with the same archaeologists and project director, Professor Marco Valenti. According to this first analysis, the majority of

visitors (regardless of age, cultural level, digital skills or background) appreciate being able to explore a rebuilt environment and interact with objects and characters in an immersive experience (Valenti 2016).

So, the shared plan was to create a video game to allow people to have a visit experience as close as possible to reality to exploit the potential of the so-called “experiential learning” (Kolb 1984; Moon 2004) in a digital playground (Bogost 2007). Furthermore, we aimed to create a video game that could function as an educational tool for schools and as an alternative to physical visits during inclement weather or other obstacles. Moreover, we wanted the game to have an educational purpose for the general public to learn while exploring the historical setting in an enjoyable way (Boyan and Sherry 2011; Mortara *et al.* 2014). Additionally, we aimed to increase accessibility for individuals who are either geographically distant or have physical limitations, as digital tools can help overcome architectural barriers that are not always removable in archaeological settings. Last but not least, we aimed to expand visitors’ knowledge of the site through the video game, showcasing two often overshadowed periods (late Medieval and early Renaissance) in addition to the well-known early medieval period already famous for being represented by the open-air museum village. That is the reason why we choose to create three different levels in the game, each one dedicated to a specific period, as if they were mini open worlds (Hiriart 2017: 171). The first one represents the early medieval village, and the selected topics are associated with the inhabitants’ main occupations; the second level is dedicated to the late medieval city of Poggio Bonizio that flourishes during this period due to the passage of the Via Francigena; the third level is dedicated to the last phase of the site and it tells about the building of the renaissance fortress commissioned by Lorenzo il Magnifico of the Medici family.

To create a fully immersive experience, the History-Game Relations framework (Cassone and Thibault 2016) was utilized. The HGR framework is an analytic tool for scholars and designers alike, capable of taking into account all the layers and processes necessary to transform History in the setting of a game. In particular, the framework follows a semiotic approach and focuses on the intersection of the three processes needed for creating a historical discourse (setting, modelling and representing) (Lozano 1987) and on the three translations that the past undergoes to become a game: perspectival, digital and ludic.

The Living Hill game revolves around a first-person story. The player’s main quest is to return three objects collected by a little girl who used to visit their grandfather in Poggibonsi during the 1910s to their rightful owners, each of whom lives in one of the three periods. When starting the game, upon discovering a small box in the attic, the girl’s ghost appears and transports the player back in time to each of the three epochs. Each period in the game has specific characters and missions that encourage players to explore the environment, collect items, and gain information to progress. Interactions with characters offer 2-3 options, each with different outcomes and reactions while several info points allow optional learning on specific objects and activities, similar to Discovery Tours in Assassin’s Creed games (Poiron 2021; Politopoulos *et al.* 2019). However, despite the opportunity offered of exploring the three historical environments, *The Living Hill* differ from a walking simulator or a virtual tour since players’ agency is fundamental to discover information within the system, advance in the game and complete the quests (Mortara *et al.* 2014: 318). As a video game, it engages players and teach them things through procedural rhetoric, which players “read” through direct engagement and criticism (Bogost 2007: 233-261; Copplestone 2017: 86).

When discussing the visual aspects of the game, we must address the accuracy and perception of the reconstructions based on the archaeological record (Copplestone 2016). This is similar to the issue archaeologists faced when building the open-air museum and reconstructing huts. As archaeologists, our discipline deals with interpreting traces (or their absence), often related to poorly preserved structures or complex sequences of events rather than seeking “truth”. When setting up the approach for the video game, we strictly followed archaeological methods for data interpretation, historical sources analysis, and case studies comparison to fill in gaps with plausible features (Figure 2). This goal required researchers, developers, and graphic designers to balance entertainment and scientific accuracy (Ibrahim and Ali, 2018).

The 3D game environment reconstruction (Mortara and Catalano, 2018) began with a photogrammetric survey of the hill using a DJI Phantom 4 drone. The digital images were then processed in Agisoft Metashape software (1.8.4 version) to obtain a 3D model of the terrain including the archaeological evidence and open-air museum structures. However, to allow players to explore inside digital replicas of huts, the entire game environment was rebuilt using 3D graphics software. A first attempt to test Unity 3D tools was unsatisfactory, so we switched to Blender (version 2.91). The 3D models were later imported into Unity (version 2020.3.19f1) for programming.

Figure 2: The reconstruction of the granary: a) the postholes identified during the excavation and the hypothetical reconstruction; b) the reconstructed structure at the open-air museum; c) the photogrammetric model; d) the hut in Blender; e) the hut in the game.

Preliminary Results: the Game Prototype

When *The Living Hill* project began, the strategy arranged with the archaeologists working on the site was to create a mobile video game. However, during development, a PC version was also considered to enhance the player's experience with the high-quality reconstructions. Nevertheless, in this regard, several accuracy issues needed addressing.

The reconstruction of the first-level environment was made easier by the physical reference of the open-air museum structures and the work of archaeologists in re-enactment activities, including costumes, character names, definitions, and storytelling (Valenti 2019). Even the characters' design was based on real archaeologists' appearance, making them easily identifiable for visitors. This high level of detail set a standard, motivating us to maintain similar accuracy in designing the other two levels, despite lacking a comparable material asset for reconstruction.

The only remains of the XIII-century settlement we planned to use as the second-level setting are a few layers of block stones at the centre of the hill (Francovich and Valenti 2007), now often hidden by grass. Fortunately, we had professional drawings made for the volume dedicated to the site and based on the archaeological record to rely on for our reconstructions (Inklink 2007). Since the settlement in this period was very large, we selected a specific area of the site represented by the main road (Via Francigena) connecting the two main churches. Today, this area (Figure 3) is still recognizable as the remains of the churches are visible and the present road closely follows the ancient path. For this level, the names of the characters were in some cases invented or omitted; in other cases, we used the names used by the same archaeologists during a one-time re-enactment event dedicated to this period, and in the case of the name of one of the notable men in Poggio Bonizio, we used the real name carved in a lead seal found during the excavation (Francovich and Valenti 2007: 184).

Lastly, we set the scene in front of the citadel for the third level dedicated to the construction of the Renaissance fortress at the beginning of the XVI century. In this case, the reconstructed fortress walls limit the space unrealistically, as the area would have been more extensive during that time, even if it was empty due to the previous settlement being destroyed. We used one of the information points to clarify this creative choice to players. The primary reference for this level was another drawing from the main publication volume (Inklink 2007) and a book edited by the architect, Luciana Masi (1992), who studied the fortress construction site. While conducting her research, she also consulted the historical archives of the

Medici family, which contain detailed records of the construction site's activities. These documents were useful for our project as they contain information regarding the names, roles, pay, and other interesting details of the individuals who worked at the construction site. This game level representing the ambitious architectural project included humble workers (such as a stonemason and a furnace men), suppliers of raw materials, the construction site manager for the Medici family, and the architect Antonio da Sangallo, brother of Giuliano, who had previously worked on the fortress design with Lorenzo il Magnifico.

Figure 3: Late Medieval remains on the hill and archaeological interpretation (the Via Francigena in red); 3D reconstruction in Blender on the basis of a reconstructive drawing (the selected area and the Via Francigena in red); 3D environment textured; game frame.

At present, the game can only be accessed through the PC platform. The mobile version of the game still has some technical issues and bugs related to the mechanics. Moreover, we are also working on finding a solution to make it available in the app stores, as the file size of the game is quite large for a standard mobile application (around 1.5 GB). To address the issue, we attempted to optimize the file by reducing polygons and texture quality. However, this negatively impacted the game's visual resolution. The programmer suggested a potential solution involving partitioning the game into smaller packages that can be downloaded as needed, but this will require a significant restructuring of the game.

Currently, our plan is to continue with the testing with different audiences and then release the PC version on the open-air museum website as a free download. The team is also exploring the possibility of releasing the assets and game code as open source after the game's official launch. This will allow the community to create their own stories within the landscape and architecture of the project, which could be advantageous for increasing public outreach and community engagement. Moreover, in the future, we also aim to have the game accessible on dedicated computer stations located inside the fortress's citadel. Additionally, we will continue to develop the mobile version in the coming months.

UX Evaluation: Pilot Testing and First Results

So, once a video game is created, how can we try to answer the last question prompted by Champion: "How will we know if we have succeeded?"

While several video games dedicated to archaeological and cultural content have been developed in Italy recently, the literature still stresses a lack of significant, extensive user tests. Games' effectiveness in learning outcomes is still understudied mainly due to the complexity of assessing intangible measures (Bellotti *et al.* 2013). Further research is necessary to investigate in greater detail the actual effectiveness of the various types of video games, to define a methodology based on metrics and evaluation tools (Bellotti *et al.* 2010), even more so those with cultural/archaeological content (Konstantakis and Caridakis 2020). Games applied to cultural heritage have proven to potentially be an independent instrument, capable of bringing information, lasting engagement, knowledge, and curiosity to a very diversified public. So, how do we assess these further aspects?

In order to answer this very complex question, a multi-level analysis was planned as a consistent extension of the project. Since *The Living Hill* aims to reach a broad audience, the study will use surveys, interviews, and focus groups to gather feedback from various group of players: middle and high school students, archaeology students and professionals, and the general public. The archaeologists managing the site have given positive feedback on the PC version during development, while evaluation of the general public's experience has only just begun.

In the general public case, the most complex to be surveyed considering the diverse range of individuals involved, a prototype questionnaire was created and tested during a public event hosted by the Foundation of Musei Senesi (the network that brings together 45 museums in the territory of Siena, including the open-air museum of Poggibonsi) and the University of Siena at the Botanic Garden of the city. On this occasion, participants were given the chance to play the video game and provide feedback through answering questions about their experience (Dawson *et al.* 2020: 256-262).

Although the context was not suitable for an accurate survey, as players only experienced partial gameplay due to participating in almost 30 different activities proposed in various stands, leaving insufficient time to finish the game (it takes about one hour to complete it), and being disrupted by others walking and chatting around, it was still the first opportunity to test the game and users' experience analysis method. Some promising assessments have already been made on similar occasions (Birchall *et al.* 2012; Pagano *et al.* 2015; Pagano *et al.* 2020), and the methodology adopted (test, observation, questionnaire and a cross-referenced data analysis) could be easily applied to *The Living Hill* case study.

The survey featured a comprehensive mix of closed-ended questions, a Likert-scale rating section, and targeted open-ended questions. It consisted of three main parts. The first included demographic questions about gender, age, affiliation, video game experience (also related to cultural heritage game projects), and knowledge of the archaeological site. The second section focused on players' experiences with *The Living Hill*, asking them to rate the game based on entertainment, education, immersion, and authenticity (Coplestone, 2016). Participants were also asked to identify difficulties, most and least effective features, how they felt during the game, and aspects they would improve. Lastly, the survey explored players' willingness to play again and their learning perception.

During the four-hour event, 24 players from Siena and its surrounding areas filled out the questionnaire, with 12 male and 12 female participants aged between 12 and 56. The majority of respondents (almost 80%) were middle or high school students, while three were undergraduates and one held a Doctor of Philosophy degree. More than a third of the respondents (37.5%) had visited the archaeological park of Poggibonsi at least once. Fifteen respondents (all under 40) stated they liked video games. Of these, 73,3% ($n = 11$) play at least one hour a week (some of the most cited titles are Minecraft, Call of Duty, Roblox, The Last of Us, and Fifa Mobile), mostly (80%) using a computer (nearly half of them also uses a console) while 20% prefers mobile devices. None of the respondents had ever played a video game created for an archaeological site, ancient civilization or historical period with educational purposes before.

In the second section of the survey, it was noted that none of the players were able to reach the second level of the game. As a result, the players' experience was limited to the early-medieval village level as expected. During the testing phase of the game, the average duration of a single game session ranged between 10 and 20 minutes. However, there were three players, all over 40 years old, who gave up almost immediately (they were not included in the survey). On the other hand, there were also four players who returned to play the game later, when the public pressure was less intense. This was mainly due to the fact that only two computers were available for testing the game.

The overall satisfaction level, entertainment, education, authenticity, immersion grades, and site enhancement were measured on a 5-grade meter, from value = 1 to value = 5 (Table 2). From the question

regarding the authenticity grade, respondents are $n = 21$. The analysis was inspired by the UX approach applied by Dawson *et al.* (2020).

	Total	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8
Overall Satisfaction	3.62	3.75	3.50	3.71	3	3.2	4.3	3.75	3.5
Entertainment	3.50	3.50	3.50	3.57	3	3.2	4	3.75	3.25
Education	4	3.75	4.25	4.14	3	4.2	3.67	4	4
Authenticity	3.71	2.67	4.50	3.5	5	3.2	5	4.25	4
Immersion	3.43	2.33	4.25	3.17	5	3	4.5	3	3.75
Site Enhancement	4.43	4	4.75	4.33	5	4.2	5	4.33	4.5

Table 2: Mean Values from the Statistics of Likert-scale rating questions (section two). Comparative analysis of how various groups of players evaluated general attractiveness, entertainment grade, educational grade, authenticity grade, immersion grade, and site enhancement. Note: Group 1 = male players; Group 2 = female players; Group 3 = under-forty age group; Group 4 = over-forty age group; Group 5 = players with high-level gaming experience; Group 6 = players with low-level gaming experience; Group 7 = players who had visited the archaeological park; Group 8 = players who had not visited the archaeological park.

As underlined in Figure 4, when asked about the difficulties encountered during the game session, most players under 40 with a high gaming experience reported no problems. On the contrary, players over 40 with a lower level of gaming experience declare they had difficulty figuring out what to do and how to use the controls (WASD keys in combination with mouse/look). However, during game sessions, players' abilities improved in just a few minutes of testing, as reported by respondents.

Figure 4: Difficulties encountered during the game session (percentages) ($n=21$).

The game received praise for its dialogues, engaging character interactions, narrative which allows players to go back in time, and historical reconstruction. The responses provided were consistent with the results of the initial analysis conducted on the public of the open-air museum. However, younger users criticized the static graphic design of characters and suggested adding more detail (as emerged in Poullis *et al.* 2019). As a matter of fact, making them walk or perform activities linked to their occupation was already part of our plans to improve realism.

During the game session, players were also asked to report their attitude and feelings by selecting from a list of definitions and providing their perception. The results were in line with their game experience: "interested" ($n=11$), "free" ($n=7$), "challenged" ($n=7$) were selected by those who reported an overall positive experience while "frustrated" ($n=2$, in combination with "interested" and "challenged") was selected by those players who had difficulties.

In the last part of the survey, as illustrated in Figure 5, players were asked to evaluate the project from a promotional and educative point of view. During the game, 66.7% of players ($n=16$) reported learning

something new, including details about life in an IX-century village, various occupations of the inhabitants, and how to use a video game. Additionally, three players expressed increased engagement and interest in the historical period, and wished to play again.

Figure 5: Responses ($n=24$) to the questions; a) “How effective do you think a game like *The Living Hill* can be to promote and make people appreciate an archaeological site?”; b) “Would you like to play similar video games dedicated to other archaeological sites, museums, ancient civilisations, or historical periods?”; c) “Would you like to play *The Living Hill* again?”; d) “Do you think you learned something you did not know by playing this game?”.

To summarise, general observations of users revealed a great sense of curiosity towards the game application as observed in Pagano *et al.* 2015 and Merchán *et al.* 2023. The first evaluation identified that players with low game experience found it difficult to manage controls and showed some bias towards video games. Younger players noted a lack of realism, especially in character animation, due to their familiarity with AAA titles (Poullis *et al.* 2019: 12).

As expected, the virtual exploration requires interaction skills that enable users to learn cultural aspects and gaming abilities through the learn-by-doing doctrine. Although the first moments may be challenging, even non-gamers can benefit. The most appreciated features (engaging storytelling, accurate reconstruction and characters’ interaction) are helpful in situating the learning (Catalano *et al.* 2014), stimulating the "irrational" part of individuals and generating motivation (Shih *et al.* 2015: 206-207). This is the first aspect that pushes people to adopt technological solutions and facilitates the learning process (Goleman, 1995). Eventually, the overall consideration of the project objectives (education and site enhancement) and the curiosity generated by an “unusual” medium to promote knowledge and participation look promising.

According to the analysis, *The Living Hill* project provides an immersive and (pro)active digital cultural heritage experience through storytelling, emotional features, and accurately reconstructed environments, resulting in success as confirmed by other works (Konstantakis and Caridakis 2020; Rice 2014). However, additional investigation is needed, especially to better evaluate the components analysed in Table 2. The results may have been affected by the testing context and limited time, particularly in regards to the sense of immersion, which had the lowest values.

Conclusion

In the previous sections, the workflow adopted for creating of *The Living Hill* was illustrated with particular attention to context and expected audience. The choices were explained in relation to the

project's objectives, the analysis conducted on the average visitors of the open-air museum, and the contingent issues we had to face during the development phase. The accuracy issues with the game's narrative and visual environment were easily resolved since the archaeologists working on the site were compelling in explaining why accuracy should have been an integral aspect of this kind of game, and the developers agreed. It was obvious to everyone how the objectives of the C.A.P.I. project were intrinsically tied to the potential of video games to act as authoritative sources of information for a cultural heritage project.

This does not mean that video games can be automatically applied to any cultural site/museum/content without a critical analysis of the purposes, a precise choice of themes, a particular focus on a) the expected audience, b) an appropriate understanding of the video game system and c) an excellent knowledge of the historical/cultural context. A thorough analysis of these factors may lead to alternative choices for game type, narrative, and visuals or even lead to entirely different kinds of tools for communicating our research, even if creating a video game for cultural heritage is currently popular (some recent examples are presented in Table 1 and discussed in Bonacini and Giaccone 2022; Mariotti 2021). The cited titles are among those listed in the map of games fully or partially based in Italy and involving to the Italian cultural heritage and landscape created by the Italian Videogame Program, IVIPRO 2023).

Nowadays, video games serve multiple purposes, including meeting archaeological aims and acting as a valuable medium for archaeological heritage dissemination and enhancement (Mariotti 2021). However, video games dedicated to cultural heritage cannot become a panacea or, worse, a cool and innovative excuse for not seriously dealing with significant actions to promote knowledge and public involvement. That is why a serious examination should be conducted to assess how video games affect users' learning and knowledge of a specific context before and after creating the game.

In conclusion, a meaningful project cannot be separated from a) a previous careful analysis of the objectives, the context, and the expected audience; b) a contextual effort to collaborate between the various domain experts (archaeologists, developers, graphics) to make the best choices based on the primary analysis; c) a final evaluation of the project (Bonacchi and Moshenska 2015) to identify its strengths and weaknesses (and eventually solve the latter).

Meeting visitors' needs and expectations within cultural spaces and providing people with significant experiences regarding the past is crucial to stimulating knowledge and learning, engaging visitors, and making them care about cultural heritage. Since the proliferation of video games dedicated to the past, the development of a creation and evaluation methodology to suggest a series of best practices to be applied to different case studies and measure users' experience will seem helpful and meaningful for many researchers and practitioners not only in the heritage field but also for those working in digital applications companies.

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Data availability

The raw data file related to the questionnaire is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305896>.

Conflict of interest disclosure

The author declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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References

- Amoroso, M. 2020. Videogame archeologici e storici: luci, ombre e lezioni imparate con Mi Rasna in Pescarin, S. (ed.) *Videogames, Ricerca, Patrimonio Culturale*: 55-59. Milano: Franco Angeli.
- Andreu Pintado, J., P. Serrano Basterra and I. Ibero Iriarte 2022. Old wine in new wineskins: a video game with epigraphic content in Andreu, J., A. Redentor and E. Alguacil (eds) *Valete vos viatores. Travelling through Latin inscriptions across the Roman Empire*: 63-94. Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra.
- Ariese, C.E., K.H.J. Boom, B. van den Hout, A.A.A. Mol and A. Politopoulos (eds) 2021. *Return to the Interactive Past. The Interplay of Video Games and Histories*. Leiden: Sidestone Press
- Bekele, M.K., R. Pierdicca, E. Frontoni, E.S. Malinverni and J. Gain 2018. A survey of augmented, virtual, and mixed reality for cultural heritage. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage* 11(2): 1-36. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3145534>.
- Bellotti, F., R. Berta, A. De Gloria 2010. Designing Effective Serious Games: Opportunities and Challenges for Research. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning* 5(3): 22-35.
- Bellotti, F., B. Kapralos, K. Lee, P. Moreno-Ger and R. Berta 2013. Assessment in and of Serious Games: An Overview. *Advances in Human-Computer Interaction* Volume 2013: 1-11. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/136864>.
- Bertoldi, S. 2021. C.A.P.I. Project in the Making: 3D Applications at Poggio Imperiale Between Materiality and Virtual Reality (Poggibonsi, IT). *Open Archaeology* 7(1): 1444-1457. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/opar-2020-0201>.
- Bertoldi, S., and S. Mariotti (eds) 2022. *The Past as a Digital Playground. Archaeology, Virtual Reality and Video Games*. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Birchall, D., M. Henson, A. Burch, D. Evans and K. Haley Goldman 2012. Levelling up: Towards best practice in evaluating museum games in Museums and the web conference: 11-14. [http://www.museumsandtheweb.com/mw2012/papers/levelling_up_towards_best_practice_in_evaluat_i.html last accessed 03/10/2023].
- Bogost, I. 2007. *Persuasive Games. The Expressive Power of Videogames*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- Bollwerk, E. 2015. Co-Creation's Role in Digital Public Archaeology. *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 3(3): 223-234. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7183/2326-3768.3.3.223>.
- Bonacchi, C. 2013. The development of Public Archaeology in Italy: a review of recent efforts. *Public Archaeology* 12(3): 211-216. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1179/1465518714Z.00000000044>.
- Bonacchi, C. and G. Moshenska 2015. Critical Reflections on Digital Public Archaeology. *Internet Archaeology* 40. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.40.7.1>.
- Bonacini, E. 2023. *Storytelling culturale e piattaforme digitali. Manuale pratico con case study e best practice internazionali*. Palermo: Dario Flaccovio Editore.
- Bonacini, E. and S.C. Giaccone 2022. Gamification and cultural institutions in cultural heritage promotion: a successful example from Italy. *Cultural Trends* 31(1): 3-22. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2021.1910490>.
- Boyan, A. and J.L. Sherry 2011. The Challenge in Creating Games for Education: Aligning Mental Models With Game Models. *Child Development Perspectives* 5(2): 82-87. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-8606.2011.00160.x>.

- Camera di Commercio Arezzo-Siena 2023. Attrattività turistica nel territorio della provincia Siena arrivi presenze tipologia struttura [<https://www.as.camcom.it/attrattivita-turistica-nel-territorio-della-provincia-siena-arrivi-presenze-tipologia-struttura>, last accessed 25/08/2023].
- Catalano, C.E., A.M. Luccini and M. Mortara 2014. Best practices for an effective design and evaluation of serious games. *International Journal of Serious Games* 1(1): 1-13. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17083/ijsg.v1i1.8>.
- Cassone, V.I. and M. Thibault 2016. The HGR Framework: A Semiotic Approach to the Representation of History in Digital Games. *gamevironments* 5: 156-204. DOI: <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:gbv:46-00105661-11>.
- Champion, E.M. 2015. *Critical gaming: interactive history and virtual heritage*. Surrey: Ashgate.
- Champion, E.M. 2017. Bringing Your A-Game to Digital Archaeology: Issues with Serious Games and Virtual Heritage and What We Can Do About It. *The SAA Archaeological Record* 17(2): 24-27.
- Champion, E.M. (ed.) 2021. *Virtual Heritage: A Guide*. London: Ubiquity Press.
- Copplestone T.J. 2017. Designing and Developing a Playful Past in Video Games in Mol, A.A., C.E. Ariese-Vandemeulebroucke, K.H.J. Boom and A. Politopoulos (eds) *The Interactive Past. Archaeology, Heritage, and Video Games*: 85-97. Leiden: Sidestone Press.
- Copplestone, T.J. 2016. "But that's not accurate: the differing perceptions of accuracy in cultural-heritage videogames between creators, consumers and critics". *Rethinking History* 21(3): 415-438. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642529.2017.1256615>.
- Cozza, M., S. Isabella, P. Di Cuia, A. Cozza, R. Peluso, V. Cosentino, L. Barbieri, M. Muzzupappa and F. Bruno 2021. Dive in the Past: A Serious Game to Promote the Underwater Cultural Heritage of the Mediterranean Sea. *Heritage* 4: 4001-4016. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage4040220>.
- Dawson, B., P. Joseph, P., and E.M. Champion 2020. Evaluating User Experience of a Multimedia Storyteller Panorama Tour: The Story of the Markham Car Collection. *Collections*, 16(3): 251-278. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1550190620940966>.
- De Felice, G. 2015. Racconti dalla terra. L'archeologia fra linguaggi, creatività e tecnologie in M.L. Gualandi, G. Gattiglia and F. Anichini (eds) *Opening the Past 2014. Immersive Archaeology. MapPapers 1-IV*: 24-27. Roma: Edizioni Nuova Cultura.
- De Felice, G. 2022. *Taras e i doni del mare*. Una mostra virtuale fra pandemia e ritorno alla normalità in Degl'Innocenti, E., D. Leone, M. Turchiano and G. Volpe (eds) *Taras e i doni del mare*: 123-126. Bari: Edipuglia.
- Di Pietro, G. 2021. Changes in Italy's education-related digital divide. *Economic Affairs* 41(2): 252-270. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecaf.12471>.
- Economu, M. 2015. Heritage in the Digital Age in W. Logan, M.N. Craith and U. Kockel (eds) *A Companion to Heritage Studies*: 215-228. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118486634.ch15>.
- Fazio, G., D. Malfitana, S. Fricano, A. Mazzagli and E. Bonacini 2022 (eds). *Il Digital Cultural Heritage e i Serious Game: l'Esperienza del Progetto* Augustus. Palermo: Palermo University Press.
- Ferdani, D., B. Fanini, M.C. Piccioli, F. Carboni and P. Vigliarolo 2020. 3D Reconstruction and Validation of Historical Background for Immersive VR Applications and Games: The Case Study of the Forum of Augustus in Rome. *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 43:129-43. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2019.12.004>.
- First Playable Found 2021. Ministero delle Imprese e del Made in Italy, fondo per l'intrattenimento digitale [<https://www.mimit.gov.it/it/incentivi/fondo-per-l-intrattenimento-digitale>, last accessed 30/08/2023].
- Francovich, R and Valenti, M (eds) 2007. *Poggio Imperiale a Poggibonsi. Il Territorio, lo Scavo, il Parco*. Milano: Silvana Editoriale.
- Fronza, V., A. Nardini, F. Salzotti and M. Valenti 2000. A GIS Solution for Excavations: Experience of the Siena University LIAAM in Z. Stancic and T. Veljanovski (eds) *Computing Archaeology for Understanding the Past. Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology. Proceedings of the 28th Conference, Ljubljana, April 2000*: 173-177. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Giordano, F. 2020. Nel mezzo del periglioso tragitto. Istituzionalizzazione e riconoscimento accademico della cultura del videogioco in Italia in Carbone, M.B. and R. Fassone (eds) *Il videogioco e l'Italia: Storie, rappresentazioni, contesti*: 283-295. Milano-Udine: Mimesis Edizioni.

- Giovannella, C., L. Cianfriglia and A. Giannelli 2022. The Italian School Ecosystems two years after the lockdown: an overview on the "digital shock" triggered by the pandemic in the perceptions of schools' principals and teachers in Dascalu, M., P. Marti, and F. Pozzi (eds) *Polyphonic Construction of Smart Learning Ecosystems. SLERD 2022. Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies*, 908: 47-76. Singapore: Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5240-1_4.
- Goleman, D. 1995. *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. London: Bloomsbury.
- Hageneuer, S. (ed.) 2020. *Communicating the Past in the Digital Age. Proceedings of the International Conference on Digital Methods in Teaching and Learning in Archaeology (12–13 October 2018)*. London: Ubiquity Press. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/bch>.
- Hiriart, J.F.V. 2017. Designing and Using Game Environments as Historical Learning Contexts in J.B Glover, J. Moss and D. Rissolo (eds) *CAA 2017: Digital Archaeologies, Material Worlds (Past and Present). Proceedings of the 45th annual conference on computer applications and quantitative methods in archaeology*: 169-177. Tubingen: Tubingen University Press. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.15496/publikation-43219>.
- Huggett, J. 2019. Resilient scholarship in the digital age. *Journal of Computer Applications in Archaeology* 2(1): 105–19. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/jcaa.25>.
- Ibrahim, N. and N.M. Ali 2018. A Conceptual Framework for Designing Virtual Heritage Environment for Cultural Learning. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage* 11(2): 1-27. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3117801>.
- Inklink 2007. Parco di Poggibonsi [<https://www.inklink.it/portfolio/parco-poggibonsi/>, last accessed 29/08/2023]
- IVIPRO 2023. Italian Videogame Program, Map of Games [<https://ivipro.it/it/italia-in-gioco/>, last accessed 02/10/2023]
- Kolb, D. 1984. *Experiential Learning: Experience as the Source of Learning and Development*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall.
- Konstantakis, M. and G. Caridakis 2020. Adding Culture to UX. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage* 13(1): 1–17. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3354002>.
- Lozano, J. 1987. *El discurso histórico*. Madrid: Alianza.
- Mariotti, S. 2020a. What if “Lara Croft” Becomes a Video Game Designer? When Archaeologists “Dig” Serious Games, in I. Marfisi-Schottman, F. Bellotti, L. Hamon and R. Klemke (eds) *Games and Learning Alliance. GALA 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science 12517*. Cham: Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-63464-3_37.
- Mariotti, S. 2020b. Serious Games and Archaeology: Rough Notes on Crafting Archaeological Data for Heritage Enhancement, in A. de Carvalho Antunes, G. Angiliu, M. Bellanova (eds) *Advances in Cultural Heritage Studies, Year 2020. Contributions of the European Students' Association for Cultural Heritage*: 217-234. Oeiras: Mazu Press.
- Mariotti, S. 2021. The Use of Serious Games as an Educational and Dissemination Tool for Archaeological Heritage. Potential and Challenges for the Future. *magazén* 2(1): 119-138. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.30687/mag/2724-3923/2021/03/005>.
- Mariotti, S and N. Marotta 2020. Gioco e *storydoing*: strumenti didattici per l'insegnamento della storia nella scuola primaria. *Didattica della Storia – Journal of Research and Didactics of History* 2(15): 608-29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.2704-8217/11224>.
- Masi, L. 1992. *La fortezza di Poggio Imperiale a Poggibonsi. Un prototipo di cantiere dell'architettura militare del Rinascimento*. Poggibonsi: Lalli Editore.
- Merchán, M.J., P. Merchán and E. Pérez 2023. Serious Games to Enhance Education. Play, Technology and Archaeology in a Spanish Museum. *Revista Colombiana de Educación* 89: 59-85. DOI: <https://doi.org/110.17227/rce.num88-13992>.
- Modena, E. 2019. Musei nei videogiochi | Videogiochi nei musei. *pianoB. arti e culture visive* 4(1): 83-105. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.2531-9876/10251>.
- Mol, A.A., C.E. Ariese-Vandemeulebroucke, K.H.J. Boom and A. Politopoulos (eds) 2017. *The Interactive Past. Archaeology, Heritage, and Video Games*. Leiden: Sidestone Press.
- Moon, J.A. 2004. *A Handbook of Reflective and Experiential Learning: Theory and Practice*. Routledge: New York.

- Morgan, C. 2019. Avatars, monsters, and machines: A cyborg archaeology. *European Journal of Archaeology* 22(3): 324–37. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/eea.2019.22>.
- Mortara, M. and C.E. Catalano 2018. 3D Virtual environments as effective learning contexts for cultural heritage. *Italian Journal of Educational Technology* 26(2): 5-21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17471/2499-4324/1026>.
- Mortara, M., C.E. Catalano, F. Bellotti, G. Fiucci, M. Houry-Panchetti and P. Petridis 2014. Learning Cultural Heritage by Serious Games. *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 15(3): 318-25. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2013.04.004>.
- Moscatti, P. 2019. Informatica Archeologica e Archeologia Digitale. Le risposte della Rete. *Archeologia e Calcolatori* 30: 21-38. [http://www.archcalc.cnr.it/indice/PDF30/03_Moscatti.pdf, last accessed 24/08/2023].
- Mutino, S., L. Colangelo and M. Scioscia 2022. Hold the Hut, il progetto di tutela e valorizzazione della capanna arcaica di San Chirico Nuovo (Potenza, Basilicata) in Bertoldi, S. and S. Mariotti (eds) *The Past as a Digital Playground. Archaeology, Virtual Reality and Video Games*: 73-90. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Pagano, A., G. Arnone, E. De Sanctis 2015. Virtual Museums and Audience Studies. The case of “Keys To Rome” exhibition in G. Guidi, R. Scopigno, J.C. Torres, H. Graf, F. Remondino, L. Duranti, P. Brunet, S. Hazan and J. Barceló (eds) *Proceedings of the 2015 Digital Heritage International Congress, volume 1, Digitization & Acquisition. Computer Graphics & Interaction*: 373-376. New York: IEEE. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/DigitalHeritage.2015.7413905>.
- Pagano, A., A. Palombini, G. Bozzelli, M. De Nino, I. Cerato and S. Ricciardi 2020. ArkaeVision VR Game: User Experience Research between Real and Virtual Paestum. *Applied Sciences* 10(9): 3182. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10093182>.
- Pescarin, S. (ed.) 2020. Videogames, Ricerca, Patrimonio Culturale. Milano: Edizioni Franco Angeli.
- Pescarin, S., B. Fanini, D. Ferdani, K. Misfud and A. Hamilton 2020. Optimising Environmental Educational Narrative Videogames: The Case of ‘A Night in the Forum’. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage* 13(4): 1-23. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3424952>.
- Piano Nazionale Scuola Digitale 2015. [<https://www.miur.gov.it/scuola-digitale> last accessed 03/10/2023]
- Pietroni, E. 2020. Ibridazione dei media nelle applicazioni interattive in Pescarin, S. (ed.) *Videogames, Ricerca, Patrimonio Culturale*: 150-174. Milano: Franco Angeli.
- Poiron, P. 2021. Assassin's Creed Origins-Discovery Tour: A Behind the Scene Experience. *Near Eastern Archaeology* 84(1): 79–85.
- Politopoulos, A., A.A.A. Mol, K.H.J. Boom and C.E. Ariese 2019. “History Is Our Playground”: Action and Authenticity in Assassin’s Creed: Odyssey. *Advances in Archaeological Practice*, 7(3): 317–323. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2019.30>.
- Poullis, C., M. Kersten-Oertel, J.P. Benjamin, O. Philbin-Briscoe, B. Simon, D. Perissiou, S. Demesticha, E. Markou, E. Frentzos, P. Kyriakidis, D. Skarlatos and S. Rizvic 2019. Evaluation of “The Seafarers”: A serious game on seaborne trade in the Mediterranean sea during the Classical period. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 12: 1-14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.daach.2019.e00090>
- Reinhard, A. 2018. *Archaeogaming: An Introduction to Archaeology in and of Video Games*. New York/Oxford: Berghahn Books.
- Rice, H.E. 2014. *Exploring the Pedagogical Possibilities of applying Gaming Theory and Technologies to Historic Architectural Visualisation*. MSc Dissertation in Digital Heritage, University of York (Department of Archaeology).
- Richardson, L. 2013. A Digital Public Archaeology? *Papers from the Institute of Archaeology* 23(1): 1-12, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5334/pia.431>.
- Ripanti, F. 2022. *Unforgettable Encounters. Understanding Participation in Italian Community Archaeology*. Oxford: Archaeopress.
- Sanders, D.H. 2014. Virtual Heritage: Researching and Visualizing the Past in 3D. *Journal of Eastern Mediterranean Archaeology and Heritage Studies* 2(1): 30–47. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5325/jeasmedarcherstu.2.1.0030>.
- Shih, J.L., S.C. Jheng and J.J. Tseng 2015. A simulated learning environment of history games for enhancing players’ cultural awareness. *Interactive Learning Environments* 23(2): 191–211. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2014.997249>.

- Simon, N. 2010. *The Participatory Museum*. Santa Cruz, CA: Museum 2.0. [<https://participatorymuseum.org/read/>, last accessed 27/08/2023].
- Solima, L. 2018. Gaming for the Museums. The MANN Experience. *Economia della Cultura* 28(3): 275-290. DOI: <http://www.rivisteweb.it/doi/10.1446/91289>.
- Valenti, M. 2019. *L'Archeodromo di Poggibonsi. Un Viaggio nell'Alto Medioevo*. Bari: Edipuglia.
- Valenti, M. 2016. 'We invest in Public Archaeology'. The Poggibonsi Archaeodrome project: an alliance between people, Municipality people, Municipality and University. *European Journal of Post Classical Archaeologies* 6: 333-346.
- Valenti, M. and F. Salzotti 2017. For a participatory culture: the experience of Archeòtipo srl and the Poggibonsi Archaeodrome (Italy, prov. Siena) in M. Cerquetti (ed.) *Bridging Theories, Strategies and Practices in Valuing Cultural Heritage*: 243-259. Macerata: Edizioni Università di Macerata.
- Volpe, G. 2020. *Archeologia pubblica. Metodi, tecniche, esperienze*. Roma: Carocci.
- Volpe, G. and G. De Felice 2014. Comunicazione e progetto culturale, archeologia e società. *European Journal of Post-Classical Archaeologies* 4: 401-420.